

Legal And Social Aspects Of Gender Inequality In Global Perspective: A Case Study Of Western Countries And Status Of Women In India

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Abstract

This research paper is an attempt to analyze the delicate relationship that exists between Law and gender inequality from the social and legal perspective globally. The research also aims to compare the legal, political and social gender rights in western countries and the status of women in India. This comparison will help to suggest recommendations and solutions to address gender equality globally by 2030 (Sustainable Development Goals Target). Although, countries across the globe guarantee equality and have stringent constitutional provisions that bar systematized discrimination against women, however, women are denied proper access to opportunities and justice in many social domains. Foremost reason for the lack of ample economic opportunities for women as compared to men is denial and easy access to basic education. Resultantly, leaving them anxious and alone to face health hazards and other safety measures. Globally, women have been discriminated against with inadequate political representation, while on an everyday basis they face inequality and discrimination across all spheres. Unfortunately, women are victims of domestic violence, unfair treatment, denial of opportunities and face discrimination at their work place too. Upon closer study, it becomes evident that the stereotypical gender roles ingrained in the social fabric of every society have been the root cause of gender disparity. The conclusion in the paper highlights that despite constitutional and legal protections for women, the strongly entrenched social and cultural factors have undermined the constitutional protection for women demanding serious attention. For ensuring visible gender justice, this research study presses for an effective enforcement mechanism that promises reform in creating legal rights awareness and a conducive environment that supports the ambitions of women. This paper is an attempt to address the structured hurdles in the social and political structures that exist, creating inequalities for women and contribute meaningfully towards the ongoing discourse on global gender inequality (Batliwala, 1994).

Keywords

Global Gender Inequality, Social and Legal Framework, Constitutional Provisions, Women Rights.

Introduction

Gender equality is essentially a fundamental human right, however, there exists a glaring gap in the access to decision making power and opportunities for both men and women. From the sociological approach owing to different social roles and identities associated with men and women, both act and think differently. In almost every society the role of men is considered more valuable than a woman's. Also, the social status accorded to men, is a clear visible symbol that denotes unequal opportunities in wealth, power and status. Although women in the West and the USA have made significant advancements, there still appear visible social inequalities that women face on an everyday basis (Chafetz, 1990).

From a biological perspective, women are easily targeted for sexual violence worldwide. Feminism in all its aspects after being reviewed and applied in certain case studies helps to conclude that the circumstances for most women worldwide in the 21st century have not changed significantly. This makes women disproportionately more suitable and likely to be hired for secretarial jobs, as caregivers at home and in hospitals. A wider view on why women seem to be less powerful and accept low paying secretarial and clerical jobs or childcare, reveals the social inequalities and stereotypical gender roles that exist globally in all societies (Giddens, 2022).

Biologically, the differences between men and women also make their differences in behavior more apparent. For instance, in most cultures the outdoor warfare and hunting activities in which men indulge makes it more evident that men have a natural tendency towards aggressive behavior which women evidently lack. A wider study among world cultures makes most sociologists conclude that women are gentler and passive by nature whereas men tend to be more aggressive. However, this could also be due to cultural practices across most societies where women tend to care for their children and stay home bound whereas men participate in wars and hunting (Elshtain, 1981).

Objective of study

In a case study of identical twins with exactly similar genetic makeup, the twins demonstrated social learning in their gender differences where the twin's girl liked household work and wished to get married when she grew up, while the twin boy enjoyed playing with trucks, cars and wanted to become a police officer (Ryan, 1985).

Review of Literature

Media reports, policy briefs and international development data serve as critical tools in examining the multifaceted issue of gender inequality both in India and globally. Indian national media such as *The Hindu* has consistently highlighted women's underrepresentation in politics and the judiciary, drawing attention to systemic barriers and legislative inertia particularly in relation to the long-pending Women's Reservation Bill. Government perspectives, as seen in communications from the Press Information Bureau (PIB), present state-led initiatives like *Beti Bachao Beti Padhao* and *Mahila Shakti Kendra*, reflect official commitments to women's welfare, though often lacking critical engagement with implementation challenges.

In contrast, independent organizations like PRS Legislative Research offer rigorous analyses of gender-specific laws, including the Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace Act (2013) and the Domestic Violence Act (2005), while also evaluating the gaps in gender budgeting and accountability. Globally, international agencies such as the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) and the International Labor Organization (ILO) provide valuable comparative insights through tools like the Gender Inequality Index and gender wage gap reports, which reveal persistent disparities in labor force participation, education and health across countries. Reports from the World Health Organization (WHO) further underscore how gender intersects with global health inequities, disproportionately affecting women and girls in low and middle income countries. These global datasets and frameworks not only contextualize India's position on the gender development spectrum but also emphasize the need for intersectional, rights-based approaches to address structural inequities worldwide. Collectively, these sources underscore both progress and persistent challenges, highlighting the need for more inclusive, data-driven and globally informed strategies to advance gender justice.

Main Text**Social Construction of Gender**

Both gender and sex are socially constructed although the physical body is shaped by social forces with which it interacts (Connell, 1987). For instance, in some society's physical strength and bold attitude are a symbol of masculinity that shapes the mannerisms and body language of men (Scott Morgan, 1993). This inextricable link between sexual differences and gender identity shapes human relations (Butler, 1989). According to some sociologists, in our daily interaction with others, human beings learn to act like a boy or a girl, essentially shaping their thoughts (West and Zimmerman, 1987).

Jaen Morris, although a man by sex and a renowned travel writer but as James Morris she successfully climbed mount Everest and considered herself to be more a woman in a man's body. Therefore, she made a deliberate choice to undergo a sex change operation and live like a woman. As a woman Jaen Morris had to learn how to behave like a woman when she was more "manly" and athletic. She says there is "no aspect of assistance" that is not gendered. In some of her restaurant experiences with other male friends she was amused at how the waiter greeted her more respectfully as a woman than as a man in the same restaurant. These little subtle ways in which gender exists in our everyday life largely go unnoticed unless they are experienced through gender change (Morries, 1974).

In the context of India, gender inequality is evident across all socio economic strata, affecting women. Fundamental Rights enshrined in the Indian Constitution that was adopted in 1950, guaranteed equality in all spheres for both men and women irrespective of their gender. Prominent among these rights is the right to life and personal liberty and prohibition of discrimination based on sex which finds mention in Articles 14, Article 15 and Article 21 of the Constitution. However, it is ironic to note that the deeply rooted cultural practices and patriarchal mindset have undermined the effectiveness of these laws, leaving women marginalized (Cornwall, 2015).

Gender inequality refers to the social constructs which give a setback to women who don't enjoy similar opportunities, rights, rewards and privileges as men. The root cause of such inequality is the stratification in our society, which has a hierarchy of layers and divisions among individuals and within their families, where a superior position gets the privilege to be rewarded. Not denying that men and women have different abilities and endowments, Rothman stated that, besides many others, there are mainly three types of inequality namely, social, economic and political. This results in other inequalities such as disparity in wealth and resources, mainly influenced by family, education, culture and marriage (Rothman, 2011).

Broadly, whenever there is stratification and discrimination against women owing to their sex, it can be classified as gender inequality. Owing to the complexity of diverse social, religious and cultural norms practiced in India, gender inequality is prominently visible. According to Betielle, the complex Indian society has unequal occupational, economic, health, political and survival opportunities. These political, economic, health, educational, cultural and societal opportunities between men and women in India refer to gender inequality. The existence of gender inequality in different forms has also been highlighted by Sen. For instance, nationality inequality is widely prevalent in India, because there is preference for sons over daughters reflecting the societal desire for giving birth to boys (Das, 2006).

Law And Gender Inequality

Gender inequality manifests in multiple legal and social domains, leading to significant disparities in mortality, access to basic facilities, professional opportunities, ownership rights and education. Mortality inequality results in demographic imbalances where women experience higher rates of mortality due to systemic neglect and discrimination (Beteille, 1986). Although demographic data may not always reveal overt bias, women frequently face systemic disadvantages in accessing essential services and resources such as healthcare, sanitation and education, which further exacerbates inequality (Rothman, 2011). In the professional sphere, women often encounter barriers to employment and promotion, with workplace harassment being a pervasive yet underreported issue that contributes to hostile work environments and stunted career growth (Kaushal, 2024). Ownership inequality remains entrenched in many societies, where legal and customary norms limit women's rights to own or inherit property, thereby reducing their economic independence and decision-making power within households (Kaushal, 2024). Additionally, disparities in access to higher education restrict women's opportunities for professional advancement and leadership, reinforcing cycles of inequality (Kaushal, 2024). These intersecting inequalities underscore the critical need for robust legal reforms and enforcement mechanisms to protect women's rights and promote gender equity.

Causes of Gender Inequality

Women's subordination manifests in widespread discrimination, exploitation and violence both in the workplace and at home, contributing significantly to their lower self-esteem, reduced literacy rates, limited mobility and persistent gender disparities (Sen, 2001). Globally, women earn approximately 20% less than men on an average and in India, this wage gap is even more pronounced, with women earning 30% to 40% less than men for comparable work (International Labour Organization [ILO], 2023).

Patriarchy remains the cornerstone of gender inequality in India, with entrenched social norms placing men in dominant positions regarding property ownership and family decision-making. Nearly 80% of property in India is owned by men, further solidifying economic dependency of women (National Family Health Survey [NFHS]-5, 2021). Patriarchal dominance confines women largely to domestic roles and dowry practices continue despite legal prohibitions, reinforcing women's subjugation (Rajula, 2013).

Socialization plays a critical role in perpetuating gender inequality. From an early age, children are socialized into rigid gender roles, leading to discriminatory expectations and limiting women's opportunities. For instance, only 65.46% of Indian women are literate compared to 82.14% of men, and female school dropout rates remain high, especially in rural areas where over 70% of women remain illiterate (Census of India, 2011; Mehta, 2021). This early social conditioning restricts women's participation in education, employment and public life, thereby sustaining systemic inequality (Nagar, 2005).

The Indian Cultural Context

Culture profoundly influences daily living practices, family dynamics, communication styles, beliefs, work preferences and lifestyle choices in India. These culturally learned behaviors often reinforce social divisions, positioning men in superior, authoritative roles while women remain constrained by societal and cultural expectations (Nagar, 2005). The oppression and exploitation of women is deeply rooted in Indian society's patriarchal structure. Lerner (1986) explains that male authority is institutionalized within the family and society, systematically excluding women from power structures. This unequal gender relationship operates on material, cultural and psychological levels, reinforcing male dominance.

Kate Millett's analysis further highlights how male supremacy is embedded in family structures, property rights, patriarchal religion and marriage customs, all of which sustain male authority and subordinate women to domestic labor and limited agency in family and sexual matters (Rajula, 2013). The patrilineal joint family system entrenches this dynamic by confining women to subordinate roles, diminishing their self-worth and reinforcing male dominance. Additionally, the cultural preference for sons over daughters perpetuates gender bias, casting daughters as burdens and perpetuating discriminatory attitudes codified into societal norms and laws (Mehrotra, 2013).

Poverty disproportionately affects women in India, who constitute approximately 70% of the population living below the poverty line, despite only 30% of the total population being classified as poor. This disparity is largely due to women's limited participation in decision-making processes and their restricted access to land ownership, credit, autonomy, and economic opportunities, which collectively reinforce systemic disempowerment (Mehta, 2021). Literacy rates further reflect gender inequality, with 65.46% of literate women as compared to 82.14% of men according to the 2011 Census. This gap is more pronounced in rural areas, where 71% of women remain illiterate compared to 86% literacy among urban women. Higher dropout rates among girls, coupled with lesser freedom to pursue education, underscore continuing gender disparities (Mehta, 2021).

Women also face significant barriers to formal employment and career advancement, largely due to societal expectations around childbearing and childrearing that restrict them to domestic roles, limiting economic participation and independence (Bajaj, 2022).

Furthermore, many women lack awareness of their fundamental rights and the impact of socio-political inequalities on their lives, perpetuates unequal opportunities and entrenched traditional and cultural barriers (Bajaj, 2022).

Although the Indian Constitution enshrines provisions to combat gender inequality—such as Articles 14, 15(1), and 15(3) and guarantees in the Preamble, implementation remains inadequate. Persistent violence against women, including frequent cases of rape, exposes the judicial system's failure to uphold women's rights effectively. This gap between legal frameworks and societal realities reflects deeply ingrained cultural ideologies that continue to undermine women's empowerment, limiting their autonomy in financial and economic decision-making both at home and in the public sphere (Raju, 2013).

Types of Gender Inequality

Women and girls in India often face deprivation of basic necessities such as shelter, clothing and food. Despite numerous government initiatives and policies aimed at enhancing women's political participation, education, health and economic opportunities, systemic political, economic and social disadvantages persist. Societal attitudes continue to undermine legislative reforms and impede genuine gender equality (Bajaj, 2022). Female literacy rates in India highlight this inequality; while pre-independence literacy among women was alarmingly below 10%, significant progress has been made with literacy rates rising to 54.16% in 2001 and 65.46% in 2011 (Desai et al., 2012). However, these figures still lag behind male literacy rates, which reached 82.14% in 2011, indicating the need for sustained efforts to reduce dropout rates among girls and close the educational gender gap (Desai et al., 2012).

Labor participation further illustrates gender disparity. According to the 2011 Census, approximately 87% of women's employment is in agriculture, with only about one-quarter of the female population engaged in formal labor sectors, reflecting limited economic opportunities (Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India, 2011). In contrast, Western countries such as Sweden, Denmark and Canada have historically demonstrated higher female workforce participation rates. Globally, women are more frequently engaged in unpaid labor and receive significantly lower wages than men for the same work. In India, women typically earn 30% to 40% less than their male counterparts (International Labour Organization [ILO], 2018).

Gender imbalances are starkly evident in demographic data as well. Child sex ratio declined from 972 females per 1,000 males in earlier decades to 940 females per 1,000 males in 2011, largely due to female infanticide and sex-selective abortions (Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India, 2011). This disparity is compounded by poor reproductive health outcomes, with many women suffering from anemia, tuberculosis and other health conditions. The World Health Organization (WHO) attributes these health challenges partly to inadequate public health expenditure by the Government of India (WHO, 2012).

Political inequality also persists despite constitutional guarantees. Although the Women's Reservation Bill proposes reserving 33% of seats in legislative bodies for women, its implementation remains incomplete because deep-rooted political and social biases limit women's political participation. For instance, in the 1996 general elections, only 1,717 of 52,293 candidates were women and in the 1998 Lok Sabha elections, only 102 female candidates were fielded by political parties (Kishwar, 1999).

Women's representation in the judiciary remains disproportionately low, reinforcing stereotypes about their capabilities. In 1998, out of 380 judges, only 11 were women and by 2009, just three women served as Supreme Court Justices (PRS Legislative Research, 2019). Despite constitutional provisions safeguarding gender equality through Directive Principles, Fundamental Duties, the Preamble and Fundamental Rights, effective translation into real-world equality remains a challenge. The Indian government has also ratified numerous international human rights treaties to support women's rights and promote gender equality (Government of India, 1950; United Nations, 2020).

Articles For Gender Equality

The Constitution of India robustly enshrines gender equality through various provisions designed to guarantee equal rights protections, and opportunities for all individuals regardless of gender or social background. Article 14 ensures equality before the law and equal protection of the laws, mandating nondiscriminatory treatment across birth, ethnicity, gender and race (Government of India, 1950). Article 15(1) explicitly prohibits discrimination based on sex, ethnicity, race, nationality, or caste, while Article 15(3) empowers the State to adopt special measures for women and children, supporting legislation such as the Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace Act (2013), Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (2005) and the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act (2013) commonly known as the Nirbhaya Act (Government of India, 1950; Ministry of Women and Child Development [MWCD], 2013). Articles 16 and 16(4) guarantee equal opportunity in education and government employment, allowing affirmative action and reservations for underprivileged groups (Government of India, 1950).

Economic fairness is further emphasized by Article 39(a), which mandates the State to secure a decent standard of living and Article 39(d), which advocates equal pay for equal

work, reinforcing the principle of gender parity in the workforce (Government of India, 1950). Article 39A facilitates equal access to justice by providing legal aid irrespective of financial capacity, while Article 42 requires the State to ensure fair working conditions and maternity benefits for women (Government of India, 1950). Social welfare for marginalized communities is addressed in Articles 46 and 47, which focus on improving the educational, economic and health status of Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes and other backward classes (Government of India, 1950). The fundamental duty under Article 51(A) (e) encourages mutual respect among citizens and denounces any acts that demean women's dignity (Government of India, 1950). Political empowerment of women is institutionalized in Articles 243D and 243T, mandating at least one-third reservation for women, including those from Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes, in Panchayats and municipalities, thereby fostering their meaningful participation in local governance (Government of India, 1992).

International Commitments And Constitutional Provisions

Gender equality is globally recognized as Sustainable Development Goal 5 (SDG 5) by the United Nations, aiming to end all forms of discrimination and ensure equal opportunities for all genders (United Nations, 2015). India has demonstrated its commitment to these international standards by ratifying key global instruments such as the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) in 1993, aligning national efforts with international gender justice frameworks (United Nations Treaty Collection, 1993).

At the national level, the Indian Constitution guarantees the principle of gender equality through various provisions found in its Preamble, Fundamental Rights, and Directive Principles of State Policy. Particularly, Article 15(3) empowers the State to implement affirmative action policies favoring women to bridge gender disparities (Government of India, 1950). The establishment of the National Commission for Women in 1992 further institutionalized the mechanism for addressing women's rights violations, advising the government on policies related to women's socio-economic empowerment and legal protection (Ministry of Women and Child Development, 2020).

Legislative Measures For Women's Protection And Empowerment

India has enacted several landmark laws targeting various facets of gender-based discrimination and violence. These include the Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act (2013), Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (2005) and the Immoral Traffic Prevention Act (1956), among others (India Code, 2023). These laws collectively establish a robust legal framework aimed at safeguarding women's rights and dignity.

Policy Initiatives Promoting Women's Development

In addition to legal protections, the Indian government has launched comprehensive policies and schemes to promote women's socio-economic development. The National Policy for Empowerment of Women (2001) outlines strategies to create enabling environments for women's growth across all sectors, focusing on education, health, employment and legal rights (Government of India, 2001). The Beti Bachao Beti Padhao campaign further targets improving child sex ratios and enhancing girls' access to education and health services, reflecting the government's proactive approach to tackling gender imbalances and fostering women's empowerment (Ministry of Women and Child Development, 2015).

Recent Developments And Impact

Recent reports highlight significant progress and challenges in implementing gender equality initiatives. For instance, the Beti Bachao Beti Padhao scheme has led to an improvement in the Sex Ratio at Birth (SRB) from 918 in 2014-15 to 930 in 2023-24 (Money-control, 2025). Additionally, the National Gross Enrolment Ratio of girls in secondary education increased from 75.51% in 2014-15 to 79.4% in 2021-22 (Money-control, 2025). However, challenges persist, including high dropout rates among girls due to inadequate sanitation facilities and early marriages (Outlook India, 2024).

In 2024, India's gender budgeting reached a milestone, with the government's gender budget crossing 1% of the GDP for the first time, totaling approximately USD 38 billion across sectors (UN Women, 2024). This increase reflects a substantial commitment to women's empowerment and gender equality.

Government Policies For Gender Equality In India

The National Policy for the Empowerment of Women (2001) marked a significant step in India's institutional commitment to gender equality and women's advancement. The policy aims to create an enabling environment where women can realize their full potential by ensuring de jure and de facto enjoyment of all human rights and fundamental freedoms at par with men in all spheres of life (Government of India, 2001). It emphasizes equal access to education, healthcare, employment, vocational training, equal pay, occupational health and participation in decision-making processes that shape the country's socio-economic and political landscape (Ministry of Women and Child Development, 2020). It also underscores the importance of eliminating discrimination and

violence against women through strengthened legal systems and shifts in societal attitudes, promoted via community engagement and male participation (Kishwar, 1999). Aligned with these goals, the Women's Vocational Training Program, under the Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship. It was developed with support from the Swedish International Development Authority (SIDA) and the International Labour Organization (ILO) to economically integrate women through skill development and industrial training (ILO, 2020). This program includes components such as the Craftsmen Training Scheme (CTS), Craft Instructors Training Scheme (CITS) and customized short-term, market-driven courses. It is implemented through a network of 11 National Skill Training Institutes (NSTIs) for Women, functioning under the central government (PIB, 2021). Further, the government launched the GATI (Gender Advancement for Transforming Institutions) initiative in 2020 through the Department of Science and Technology (DST) to promote gender equity in Science, Technology, Engineering, Medicine and Mathematics (STEMM) fields. Inspired by the Athena SWAN Charter in the UK, GATI seeks to institutionalize diversity and inclusion in higher education and research institutions, ensuring a supportive environment for women's participation and progression in STEMM disciplines (UNDP, 2023; DST, 2020). Together, these interconnected policies and initiatives illustrate a multi-layered strategy to address structural gender disparities in India's public, economic and academic spheres.

Major Initiatives, Schemes And Measures Taken By The Government To Achieve Gender Equality In India

To address persistent gender inequality, the Government of India has implemented a wide range of policies and schemes aimed at empowering women and girls across multiple domains, including education, health, employment, safety and financial inclusion. One of the flagship initiatives, Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (BBBP), launched in 2015, seeks to combat the declining Child Sex Ratio (CSR) and promote the education and value of the girl child. The scheme contributed to measurable improvements in CSR in several districts, with government data indicating increased institutional deliveries and higher school enrollments for girls (Ministry of Women and Child Development, 2021). Complementing this, the Mahila Shakti Kendra (MSK) scheme has established over 300 district-level centers to offer rural women access to employment, digital literacy and skill development services (PIB, 2021). Working Women Hostels (WWH) and the National Crèche Scheme have played pivotal roles in enabling women's workforce participation by providing secure accommodation and childcare services, particularly for single or disadvantaged women (Ministry of Women and Child Development, 2020). For adolescent girls, the Scheme for Adolescent Girls (SAG) has reached nearly 10 lakh beneficiaries since its inception, delivering essential nutrition, life skills and education support for girls aged 11–18 (PRS Legislative Research, 2022). In efforts to enhance women's safety and community involvement, the Mahila Police Volunteers (MPV) initiative operational in over 12 states acts as a bridge between women in distress and local law enforcement (PIB, 2020). Economically, the Rashtriya Mahila Kosh (RMK) has enabled microcredit disbursement to more than 7 lakh women through self-help groups, enhancing their financial independence (Ministry of Women and Child Development, 2019). Schemes like the Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana have had a transformative impact, replacing traditional fuels with LPG for over 9 crore rural women, significantly reducing indoor air pollution and health risks (Ministry of Petroleum & Natural Gas, 2022; WHO, 2020). The Sukanya Samriddhi Yojana (SSY) has encouraged long-term financial planning for girls' education and marriage, with more than 2 crore accounts opened to date (PIB, 2021). Entrepreneurship schemes such as Stand-Up India have facilitated over 1.4 lakh loans to women and the Prime Minister's Employment Generation Programme (PMEGP) has supported over 7 lakh microenterprises, with women forming a significant share of the beneficiaries (Ministry of Finance, 2021; PRS Legislative Research, 2022). Digital platforms like Mahila e-Haat and Women Entrepreneurship Platform (WEP) provide visibility and e-commerce access to women-led businesses, furthering economic inclusion (NITI Aayog, 2021). Schemes like STEP and the Mahila Coir Yojana focus on sector-specific skill development, enhancing employability across traditional crafts and new-age sectors. To support victims of violence, the One-Stop Centre (OSC) and Women Helpline Scheme have together supported over 70 lakh women through integrated legal, medical, and psychosocial services (Ministry of Women and Child Development, 2021). The Ujjawala Scheme has successfully rescued and rehabilitated victims of human trafficking, offering shelter, training, and reintegration services, while the SWADHAR Greh provides shelter and legal aid to women in crisis (PRS Legislative Research, 2021). The Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY) has extended conditional cash transfers to over 1.75 crore women since 2017, improving maternal and child health indicators (NFHS-5, 2021). Programs like DAY-NULM also prioritize urban poor women by offering employment training, shelter and credit access for self-employment (Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, 2021). While these multi-sectoral interventions have contributed to progress in gender equity, challenges remain in ensuring inclusive

outreach, especially for women from marginalized castes, tribes and minority communities (Desai et al., 2010; UNDP, 2023). Strengthening implementation mechanisms, ensuring intersectionality and enhancing inter-agency coordination remain critical to achieving lasting gender justice.

Conclusion

Gender inequality in India is not just a policy failure, it is a moral crisis that continues to deny half of our population their rightful place in society. For centuries, women have been silenced, sidelined and stripped of autonomy, not by chance, but by deeply rooted systems of patriarchy, cultural bias, and institutional neglect, which must end now. Despite robust constitutional guarantees particularly under Articles 14, 15, 16, 39(a), and 42, true gender equality in India remains unrealized. While these provisions promise legal equality and protection, structural patriarchy, institutional inertia, and cultural conditioning continue to undermine women's rights and opportunities.

Recent labour data illustrates this gap. Female labour force participation has risen from 23.3% in 2017-18 to 41.7% in 2023-24 (Economic Survey, 2024; PLFS data). Yet, only 15.9% of working women hold formal salaried jobs. The majority remain in low-quality, informal or self-employed work (Reuters poll, 2025). Although more women are entering the workforce, the reality of unpaid work, safety concerns, and caregiving responsibilities continues to constrain meaningful participation (United Nations Time Use Survey, 2025).

Political representation remains bleak: women hold merely 14-15% of Lok Sabha seats, and the Women's Reservation Bill guaranteeing one-third legislative representation will only take effect from the 2029 elections (AP News; constitutional amendment). This delay underscores the dissonance between legislative intent and tangible progress.

Such disparities reflect systemic failures not statistical anomalies. Legal frameworks mean little without enforcement, and constitutional rights remain hollow absent cultural and institutional change.

Gender equality is not optional because it is central to India's democratic and developmental vision. Until every woman can participate fully in public, political, and economic life without fear, prejudice, or limitation, the promise of constitutional justice remains unfulfilled. Therefore, in my opinion, equality promised must be equality delivered.

Suggestions for the future Study

Gender inequality remains a pervasive issue in India, deeply rooted in sociocultural norms and exacerbated by legal challenges. Despite significant legislative efforts and initiatives aimed at promoting gender equality, women continue to face discrimination and violence, particularly in rural areas. Legal frameworks such as the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act and the Sexual Harassment of Women at the Workplace Act represent important strides forward; however, enforcement remains inconsistent and awareness of these laws is often limited.

To effectively combat gender inequality, a multifaceted approach is essential. First, there must be increased investment in public awareness campaigns that educate both men and women about gender rights and existing legal protections. This could foster a culture of respect and support for gender equality, encouraging community participation in challenging discriminatory practices.

Second, enhancing the accessibility and efficiency of legal mechanisms for women seeking justice is crucial. This includes training law enforcement and judicial personnel in gender sensitivity, to ensure that complaints are handled with the seriousness they deserve. Moreover, creating more women-friendly legal aid services can empower victims to seek help without fear or stigma.

Third, targeted socioeconomic programs should focus on skill development and employment opportunities for women, particularly in marginalized communities. Initiatives like the Mahila Shakti Kendra and Skill Upgradation programs can be expanded to ensure that women have access to resources and training that promotes their financial independence.

Lastly, engaging men as allies in the fight for gender equality can transform societal attitudes. Encouraging male involvement in educational programs and community initiatives can shift perceptions and promote shared responsibility for gender equality.

Overall, a comprehensive and sustained effort involving legal reforms, education and community engagement is essential to dismantle the structures of gender inequality in India, paving the way for a more equitable society. Efforts must be made to improve data collection and recruitment through robust and independent evidence-based research and program design to better address the challenges. Governments must conduct awareness-raising activities to address gender equality through workshops and advocacy efforts, involving civil society organizations, the arts and cultural organizations to broadly explore ways to promote gender equality.

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